

TURLI XALQLAR MADANIYATINI O'RGANISH ORQALI KATTA MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MILLIY VA UMUMINSONIY QADRIYATLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH

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Annotatsiya

KIRISH: maqolada turli xalqlar madaniyatini o'rganish orqali katta maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni shakllantirish muammosi ko'rib chiqiladi.

MAQSAD: maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishda turli xalqlar madaniyatini o'rganishning pedagogik imkoniyatlarini ilmiy asoslash va ochib berish.

MATERIAL VA METODLAR: tadqiqot davomida maktabgacha ta'lim bo'yicha davlat hujjatlari, axloqiy va ko'p madaniyatli ta'lim bo'yicha ilmiy ishlar, shuningdek maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari uchun uslubiy qo'llanmalar ishlatilgan. Amaliy material sifatida ertaklar, xalq o'yinlari, urf-odatlar, musiqa, illyustratsiyalar va turli xalqlar madaniyati elementlari qo'llanilgan. Tadqiqot davomida maktabgacha ta'lim bo'yicha davlat hujjatlari, axloqiy va ko'p madaniyatli ta'lim bo'yicha ilmiy ishlar, shuningdek maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari uchun uslubiy qo'llanmalar ishlatilgan. Amaliy material sifatida ertaklar, xalq o'yinlar

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, katta maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni turli xalqlar madaniyati bilan tanishtirish milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarning shakllanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bolalar urf-odatlar va urf-odatlarga qiziqishni kuchaytirdilar, boshqalarga nisbatan ochiqroq, xayrixoh va hurmatli bo'ldilar. Mashg'ulotlar jarayonida o'quvchilar o'zlarining ona madaniyatiga hurmat tuyg'usini kuchaytirdilar, muloqot, o'zaro yordam va bag'rikenglik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirdilar. Tajribadan oldin va keyin natijalarni taqqoslash maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar bilan tarbiyaviy ishlarda turli xalqlar madaniyatidan foydalanish samaradorligini tasdiqladi.

XULOSA: qilib shuni yana bir bor ta'kidlash lozimki, refleksiya kontseptual bilim va mutaxassisning shaxsiy tajribasi o'rtasidagi eng muhim, hal qiluvchi bo'g'inga aylanadi. Refleksiyani o'rganmasdan, kontseptual g'oyalar shakllanadigan professional bilimlar, go'yo ongda yetarlicha shakllanmaydi va bu harakatga bevosita rahbarlik qilishiga imkon bermaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: katta maktabgacha yosh, milliy qadriyatlar, umuminsoniy qadriyatlar, dunyo xalqlari madaniyati.

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И ОБЩЕЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ У ДЕТЕЙ СТАРШЕГО ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА С ПОМОЩЬЮ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ КУЛЬТУРЫ РАЗНЫХ НАРОДОВ.

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Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в статье рассматривается проблема формирования национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей у детей старшего дошкольного возраста посредством изучения культуры разных народов.

ЦЕЛЬ: научно обосновать и раскрыть педагогические возможности изучения культуры разных народов в формировании у детей старшего дошкольного возраста национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: в ходе исследования использовались государственные документы по дошкольному образованию, научные работы по нравственному и поликультурному воспитанию, а также методические пособия для ДОО. В качестве практического материала применялись сказки, народные игры, традиции, музыка, иллюстрации и элементы культуры разных народов. Основными методами исследования стали анализ педагогической литературы, наблюдение за деятельностью детей, беседы, изучение детских работ, а также педагогический эксперимент и диагностика уровня сформированности национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: результаты исследования показали, что знакомство детей старшего дошкольного возраста с культурой разных народов положительно влияет на формирование национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей. У детей повысился интерес к традициям и обычаям, они стали более открытыми, доброжелательными и уважительными по отношению к другим. В процессе занятий у воспитанников укрепилось чувство уважения к родной культуре, развились навыки общения, взаимопомощи и толерантности. Сравнение результатов до и после эксперимента подтвердило эффективность использования культуры разных народов в воспитательной работе с детьми дошкольного возраста.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: разнообразие используемых в этих целях средств помогает привить старшим дошкольникам чувство симпатии, уважения, дружелюбия к людям других национальностей, принять и понять национальную самобытность, обычаи и традиции, устранить зачатки национализма, нетерпимости к людям других национальностей

Ключевые слова: старший дошкольный возраст, национальные ценности, общечеловеческие ценности, культура народов мира.

FORMATION OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL VALUES AMONG OLDER PRESCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH THE STUDY OF THE CULTURE OF DIFFERENT NATIONS.

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Annotation

INTRODUCTION: the article examines the problem of the formation of national and universal values in older preschool children through the study of the culture of different nations.

PURPOSE: to scientifically substantiate and reveal the pedagogical possibilities of studying the culture of different nations in the formation of national and universal values in older preschool children.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the research used state documents on preschool education, scientific papers on moral and multicultural education, as well as methodological manuals for preschool institutions. Fairy tales, folk games, traditions, music, illustrations and elements of culture of different nations were used as practical material. The main research methods were the analysis of pedagogical literature, observation of children's activities, conversations, study of children's works, as well as pedagogical experiment and diagnosis of the level of formation of national and universal values.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS the results of the study showed that the acquaintance of older preschool children with the culture of different nations has a positive effect on the formation of national and universal values. Children have increased their interest in traditions and customs, they have become more open, friendly and respectful towards others. During the lessons, the students strengthened their sense of respect for their native culture, developed communication skills, mutual assistance and tolerance. A comparison of the results before and after the experiment confirmed the effectiveness of using the culture of different peoples in educational work with preschool children.

CONCLUSION: the variety of tools used for these purposes helps to instill in older preschoolers a sense of sympathy, respect, and friendliness towards people of other nationalities, to accept and understand national identity, customs, and traditions, and to eliminate the beginnings of nationalism and intolerance towards people of other nationalities.

Keywords: senior preschool age, national values, universal values, culture of the peoples of the world.

Preschool age is a crucial period for laying the foundations of socially significant values and moral–ethical standards. At this stage, a child begins to absorb ethical norms accepted in society, learns to evaluate actions from a moral perspective, regulate their own behavior according to these norms, and experiences ethical feelings such as empathy and compassion. Every child is born into a social environment where parents, caregivers, and teachers play a key role in the process of socialization. Acting as mediators between the child and the surrounding world, they transmit cultural ideals, norms, and values that correspond to social expectations and the child’s individual characteristics. Gradually, the child adopts social roles and attitudes, interprets them, and makes them part of their own value system.

Initially, children tend to evaluate only the actions of others, such as peers or characters in stories. By middle preschool age, however, they are already able to assess actions regardless of personal sympathy and justify their judgments. In older preschool children, relationships with peers change significantly: friendliness, willingness to help, empathy, and emotional responsiveness become more apparent, while manifestations of aggressive or instinctive behavior decrease. Although competition remains a lifelong phenomenon, by the senior preschool age children can already recognize the inner world of others—their desires, preferences, and emotional states. At the age of six, children increasingly demonstrate altruistic behaviors, such as helping, sharing, giving gifts, and showing sympathy.

During the preschool years, the foundations of national identity and respect for other cultures are also formed. Children begin to understand cultural values, traditions, and distinctive features of different peoples. A trusting and friendly atmosphere in preschool institutions is essential for fostering positive interpersonal communication. Preschool children rarely distinguish one another by nationality; therefore, educators should focus on teaching appropriate communication skills—how to ask questions, offer help, apologize, and interact respectfully. To ease communication, especially in diverse groups, children may temporarily use simplified or international names.

Intercultural education should not be limited to isolated activities such as regional content, single celebrations, or occasional games. It must represent a purposeful, systematic, and continuous process aimed at shaping a respectful worldview and a conscious attitude toward cultural diversity. This work should permeate everyday life in each preschool group and extend into family education.

The fundamental principles of intercultural communication include tactfulness in interaction with people of different national backgrounds; the understanding that nationality should not negatively affect interpersonal relationships; respect for one’s own traditions as well as those of others; an informed and thoughtful approach to discussing cultural and ethical issues; respect for the customs, rituals, and norms of the ethnic environment in which one lives; and basic knowledge of the language of the main ethnic

group. It is not necessary to know all traditions in detail—respect and openness toward other cultures are the key ethical requirements.

Educators play an important role in explaining to children that different peoples have unique traditions that may seem unfamiliar. Such differences should never become a reason for ridicule or negative attitudes. A wide range of educational tools can be used to foster intercultural ethics, including literature, illustrations, films, music, dances, and visual arts. National toys, especially dolls, are particularly effective. In senior and preparatory groups, dolls representing various cultures help children learn about traditional clothing, daily life, crafts, natural conditions, and national character traits. These dolls should accurately reflect cultural features, evoke positive emotions, and often represent characters from national literature.

The formation of intercultural communication ethics is especially effective through role-playing and active games that incorporate national attributes. Through play, children explore the social world, express curiosity, develop creativity, and deepen their understanding of cultural diversity. Folk art, music, illustrations, and folklore—such as proverbs and sayings—also contribute significantly to this process. They reflect moral norms, enrich children's speech, promote tolerance, and encourage respectful behavior. Folklore helps children understand the inner world of other cultures, reduces fear of differences, and fosters friendship and mutual understanding.

Overall, the use of diverse educational resources promotes empathy, respect, friendliness, and acceptance of cultural uniqueness among older preschool children. The most effective means of developing intercultural ethics include learning about folk traditions and rituals, engaging with literature and folklore of different peoples, using national toys, encouraging direct communication, and involving children in culturally meaningful games and activities.

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